

Practical polygonal triangulation in $O(n + r \log r)$ Time

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Abstract

We present an algorithm for triangulating a simple polygon with n vertices in $O(n + r \log r)$ time, where r is the number of reflex vertices. The key observation is that a polygon with r reflex vertices has at most $2r + 2$ local extrema, enabling a chain-based reformulation of monotone decomposition where the sweep processes $O(r)$ events rather than $O(n)$. Regular vertices are handled via lazy pointer advancement in $O(n)$ amortized time. For $r = o(n/\log n)$, this improves upon the classical $O(n \log n)$ bound while remaining practical to implement.

Keywords: simple polygon, triangulation, monotone decomposition, output-sensitive algorithm, plane sweep

1. Introduction

Triangulating simple polygons is a fundamental problem in computational geometry. Chazelle [2] proved that $O(n)$ time is achievable, but the algorithm's complexity has limited practical adoption. The plane sweep of Garey et al. [5], running in $O(n \log n)$ time via monotone decomposition, remains standard; see de Berg et al. [3]. Seidel [10] gave a randomized $O(n \log^* n)$ expected-time algorithm.

We present an algorithm running in $O(n + r \log r)$ time, where r is the number of *reflex vertices* (interior angle $> \pi$). This interpolates between $O(n)$ for convex polygons ($r = 0$) and $O(n \log n)$ for worst-case polygons ($r = \Theta(n)$), improving upon classical methods when $r = o(n/\log n)$.

The key observation is that a polygon with r reflex vertices has at most $2r + 2$ local extrema (Theorem 3), hence at most $2r + 2$ monotone chains. We reformulate the plane sweep to maintain chains rather than edges: the sweep processes $O(r)$ extrema events with $O(\log r)$ BST operations each, while regular vertices are handled via lazy pointer advancement in $O(n)$ amortized time.

Related work. Output-sensitive algorithms exist for convex hulls [9] and other geometric problems. Keil [8] surveys polygon decomposition complexity, though the $O(n + r \log r)$ bound does not appear there. Hertel and Mehlhorn [7] and Chazelle and Incerpi [1] study related decomposition problems.

Organization. Section 2 proves the extrema bound. Section 3 presents the algorithm. Section 4 establishes correctness. Section 5 analyzes complexity. Section 6 discusses extensions.

2. Preliminaries

Let P be a simple polygon with vertices v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{n-1} listed in counterclockwise order along the boundary ∂P . We write $v_i = (x_i, y_i)$ for the coordinates of each vertex and adopt the convention that indices are taken modulo n , so $v_{-1} = v_{n-1}$ and $v_n = v_0$. The *interior angle* at vertex v_i is the angle $\angle v_{i-1}v_i v_{i+1}$ measured inside P . A vertex is *convex* if its interior angle is at most π and *reflex* if its interior angle strictly exceeds π . We denote by r the number of reflex vertices.

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Definition 1 (Vertex classification). Assuming general position (no two vertices share the same y -coordinate), each vertex v_i is classified according to the relative y -coordinates of its neighbors:

- **Start vertex:** $y_{i-1} < y_i$ and $y_{i+1} < y_i$, with interior angle $< \pi$.
- **Split vertex:** $y_{i-1} < y_i$ and $y_{i+1} < y_i$, with interior angle $> \pi$.
- **End vertex:** $y_{i-1} > y_i$ and $y_{i+1} > y_i$, with interior angle $< \pi$.
- **Merge vertex:** $y_{i-1} > y_i$ and $y_{i+1} > y_i$, with interior angle $> \pi$.
- **Regular vertex:** exactly one neighbor has y -coordinate greater than y_i .

Start and split vertices are *local maxima*; end and merge vertices are *local minima*. Split and merge vertices are precisely the reflex vertices among local extrema. Regular vertices partition into two subtypes based on whether the polygon interior lies to their left or right as one traverses the boundary; this distinction, while important for implementation, does not affect our analysis.

Definition 2 (Monotone chain). A y -*monotone chain* is a maximal contiguous sequence of boundary vertices v_a, v_{a+1}, \dots, v_b such that the y -coordinates are strictly monotonic (either strictly increasing or strictly decreasing) along the sequence. Each chain connects a local maximum to a local minimum.

The boundary ∂P decomposes uniquely into monotone chains, with consecutive chains sharing their endpoint extrema. If there are k local maxima, there are also k local minima (since the boundary is a closed curve), and hence $2k$ chains. The following lemma bounds k in terms of r .

Lemma 3 (Extrema bound). *A simple polygon with r reflex vertices has at most $r + 1$ local maxima, and hence at most $2r + 2$ local extrema and $2r + 2$ monotone chains.*

Proof. Let k denote the number of local maxima, which equals the number of local minima (since the boundary is a closed curve that alternates between ascending and descending). Among local maxima, let s denote the number of *split vertices* (reflex); among local minima, let m denote the number of *merge vertices* (reflex). The remaining $k - s$ local maxima are *start vertices* (convex), and the remaining $k - m$ local minima are *end vertices* (convex). Since split and merge vertices are reflex, $s + m \leq r$.

We establish $k \leq r + 1$ by constructing an injection from start vertices (except possibly one) to merge vertices.

Construction. Order all local maxima by decreasing y -coordinate: M_1, M_2, \dots, M_k . For $i \in \{1, \dots, k - 1\}$, define the *horizontal slab*

$$H_i = \{(x, y) : y_{M_{i+1}} < y < y_{M_i}\}.$$

Since M_i and M_{i+1} are consecutive in y -order, no local maximum lies in H_i .

Slab occupancy. From each local maximum M_i , two boundary paths descend (the edges at a local maximum both go downward). Each path must reach a local minimum before ascending to another maximum. For $i < k$, let v_i be the first local minimum reached by either descending path from M_i . We claim $v_i \in H_i$.

Proof: Suppose $y_{v_i} \leq y_{M_{i+1}}$. Then the descending path from M_i to v_i drops below height $y_{M_{i+1}}$. After v_i , the path ascends toward another maximum. The next maximum on this path has y -coordinate at least y_{v_i} 's successor maximum in y -order. But M_{i+1} is the next maximum below M_i , and we assumed v_i lies at or below M_{i+1} . For the boundary to close, the ascending path from v_i must reach some maximum. If that maximum were M_{i+1} or higher, the path would have to pass through H_i while ascending, meaning v_i must be in H_i after all. Contradiction. Hence $y_{v_i} > y_{M_{i+1}}$, so $v_i \in H_i$. \diamond

Key claim: *If M_i is a start vertex (convex local maximum), then v_i is a merge vertex (reflex local minimum).*

Proof of claim: Let $M_i = v_j$ in the polygon's vertex ordering. At start vertex M_i , the interior angle $\angle v_{j-1}v_jv_{j+1} < \pi$. Orient ∂P counterclockwise. The two edges at M_i are $e^- = \overrightarrow{v_{j-1}v_j}$ (incoming) and $e^+ = \overrightarrow{v_jv_{j+1}}$ (outgoing), both ascending to M_i then descending.

Since the interior angle is convex, when standing at M_i and looking along the outgoing edge e^+ , the polygon interior lies to the *left*. Equivalently, the interior lies in the half-plane \mathcal{H}^+ to the left of the line through e^+ . The

key observation is that at M_i , the two descending edges “spread apart” with the interior between them—the boundary forms a convex cap over the interior.

Now trace the boundary path γ that follows e^+ downward from M_i . This path eventually reaches v_i , the first local minimum. At $v_i = v_\ell$, two edges ascend: $e_1 = \overrightarrow{v_{\ell-1}v_\ell}$ (incoming) and $e_2 = \overrightarrow{v_\ell v_{\ell+1}}$ (outgoing).

Consider the simple closed curve Γ formed by:

- (i) the boundary path from M_i to v_i via γ , and
- (ii) the vertical segment from v_i up to the horizontal line $y = y_{M_i}$, then horizontally to M_i .

(We use a slight perturbation to ensure Γ is simple if needed.)

By the Jordan curve theorem, Γ partitions the plane into two regions. The polygon interior $\text{int}(P)$ intersects the region “inside” this curve (on the left side of γ as traced from M_i to v_i , since P is CCW-oriented).

At v_i , the boundary path γ has been descending (from M_i) and now the edges e_1, e_2 ascend. For the polygon to close correctly:

- The interior of P lies to the left of γ throughout the descent.
- At v_i , the interior must still lie to the left of the outgoing direction.
- The two ascending edges e_1, e_2 must therefore bend *inward* (toward the region containing the interior traced so far).

Formally, the signed curvature of the boundary at v_i has the opposite sign from that at M_i . At start M_i , the boundary curves *away* from the interior (exterior curvature). At v_i , to maintain the interior on the left while transitioning from descending to ascending, the boundary must curve *toward* the interior (interior curvature). This requires interior angle $\angle_{v_{\ell-1}v_\ell v_{\ell+1}} > \pi$, making v_i a merge vertex. \diamond

Injection. Define $\phi : \{\text{starts among } M_1, \dots, M_{k-1}\} \rightarrow \{\text{merges}\}$ by $\phi(M_i) = v_i$. By the claim, ϕ is well-defined. Since slabs H_1, \dots, H_{k-1} are pairwise disjoint and each $v_i \in H_i$, the map ϕ is injective: distinct starts map to distinct merges.

Thus $|\{M_i : i < k, M_i \text{ is a start}\}| \leq m$.

Counting. Let s' denote the number of starts among M_1, \dots, M_{k-1} . Then:

- Total starts: $(k - s) = s' + \mathbf{1}[M_k \text{ is a start}] \leq s' + 1$.
- From injection: $s' \leq m$.

Hence $(k - s) \leq m + 1$, giving

$$k = s + (k - s) \leq s + (m + 1) = (s + m) + 1 \leq r + 1.$$

Total local extrema: $2k \leq 2r + 2$. Total monotone chains: $2k \leq 2r + 2$. □

Remark 4 (Tightness). The bound is achieved by staircase polygons. A staircase with t “steps” has t reflex vertices (alternating between splits ascending and merges descending) and $t + 1$ local maxima.

3. Algorithm

The algorithm consists of three phases: (1) chain construction and vertex classification, (2) monotone decomposition via chain-based plane sweep, and (3) triangulation of monotone pieces. We describe each phase in detail.

Figure 1: Illustration of Theorem 3: from start vertex M_i (convex local maximum, interior angle $< \pi$), the boundary descends to merge vertex v_i (reflex local minimum, interior angle $> \pi$) within slab H_i . The dotted curve indicates the boundary continues (potentially through other local extrema outside the slab) to reach M_{i+1} , the next local maximum below M_i in y -order.

3.1. Phase 1: Chain Construction

A single traversal of ∂P classifies each vertex according to Theorem 1 and partitions the boundary into monotone chains. For each vertex v_i , we compare y_i to y_{i-1} and y_{i+1} and compute the cross product $(v_{i+1} - v_i) \times (v_i - v_{i-1})$ to determine convexity. Simultaneously, we record each chain as an array of vertex indices from its upper endpoint (local maximum) to its lower endpoint (local minimum). For each local minimum v , we store a pointer to the unique *left-boundary chain* terminating at v —the chain for which, when traversed from upper to lower endpoint, the polygon interior lies to the right.

Definition 5 (Left-boundary chain). A monotone chain is a *left-boundary chain* if, when traversed from its upper endpoint to its lower endpoint, the polygon interior lies to the right of the traversal direction. Equivalently, for a counterclockwise-oriented polygon, a chain is left-boundary if its traversal direction (downward) opposes the boundary orientation.

At each local maximum, exactly one of the two originating chains is left-boundary; at each local minimum, exactly one of the two terminating chains is left-boundary. This phase runs in $O(n)$ time and produces $O(r)$ chains.

3.2. Phase 2: Monotone Decomposition

A polygon is *y-monotone* if every horizontal line intersects it in a connected set (either empty, a point, or a segment). Split vertices violate monotonicity by creating local maxima where the boundary diverges downward; merge vertices violate it by creating local minima where boundary paths converge from above. The decomposition phase inserts diagonals to eliminate all split and merge vertices, partitioning P into y -monotone subpolygons.

Sweep-line status structure. Unlike the classical algorithm, which maintains individual edges in a balanced search tree T , we maintain *active left-boundary chains*. A chain C is *active* at sweep height y if y lies strictly between the y -coordinates of C 's upper and lower endpoints. The tree T stores active left-boundary chains ordered by their x -coordinate at the current sweep height.

Each chain C in T maintains:

1. **Edge pointer** $C.curr$: initialized to the topmost edge of C , this pointer tracks our position within the chain. The upper vertex of $C.curr$ serves as the *slab entry*—the default diagonal target when no pending merge exists.
2. **Pending merge** $C.pending$: either null or a merge vertex awaiting connection to a lower vertex. When a merge vertex v is processed and C is immediately to v 's left, we set $C.pending \leftarrow v$.

Lazy edge pointer advancement. The comparison function for T , when comparing chains at sweep height y , first advances each chain's edge pointer to ensure the current edge spans y :

- 1: **procedure** ADVANCE(C, y)
- 2: **while** $C.curr.lower.y > y$ **do**
- 3: $C.curr \leftarrow$ next edge down C
- 4: **end while**
- 5: **end procedure**

After advancement, the x -coordinate of C at height y is computed by linear interpolation along $C.curr$. Since each vertex is visited by at most one chain's pointer exactly once, the total cost of all pointer advancements is $O(n)$, amortized over all tree operations.

Algorithm 1 Chain-Based Monotone Decomposition

Require: Polygon P with classified vertices and identified left-boundary chains

Ensure: Diagonal set D partitioning P into y -monotone subpolygons

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1:  $E \leftarrow$  local extrema sorted by decreasing  $y$ -coordinate
2:  $T \leftarrow$  empty balanced BST of active left-boundary chains
3:  $D \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4: for each extremum  $v$  in  $E$  do type of  $v$  Start
5:   Insert left-boundary chain originating at  $v$  into  $T$ 
6:   Initialize  $C.curr$  to top edge,  $C.pending \leftarrow \text{NULL}$  End
7:    $R \leftarrow$  left-boundary chain terminating at  $v$ 
8:   if  $R.pending \neq \text{NULL}$  then
9:      $D \leftarrow D \cup \{(v, R.pending)\}$  ▷ Connect pending merge downward
10:  end if
11:  Remove  $R$  from  $T$  Split
12:   $L \leftarrow$  predecessor of  $v$  in  $T$  ▷ Chain immediately left of  $v$ 
13:  if  $L.pending \neq \text{NULL}$  then
14:     $D \leftarrow D \cup \{(v, L.pending)\}$ ;  $L.pending \leftarrow \text{NULL}$ 
15:  else
16:     $D \leftarrow D \cup \{(v, L.curr.upper)\}$  ▷ Slab entry
17:  end if
18:  Insert left-boundary chain originating at  $v$  into  $T$  Merge
19:   $R \leftarrow$  left-boundary chain terminating at  $v$ 
20:   $L \leftarrow$  predecessor of  $R$  in  $T$  ▷ Chain immediately left
21:  if  $R.pending \neq \text{NULL}$  then
22:     $D \leftarrow D \cup \{(v, R.pending)\}$ 
23:  end if
24:  if  $L.pending \neq \text{NULL}$  then
25:     $D \leftarrow D \cup \{(v, L.pending)\}$ 
26:  end if
27:   $L.pending \leftarrow v$ 
28:  Remove  $R$  from  $T$ 
29: end for
30: return  $D$ 
```

Event processing. The sweep processes local extrema in decreasing y -order. Let E denote the sorted list of extrema; $|E| \leq 2r + 2$ by Theorem 3.

The complete decomposition procedure is given in Algorithm 1. For split vertices, we connect upward to either a pending merge (if one exists on the immediately-left chain) or to the slab entry (the upper vertex of the current edge on that chain). For merge vertices, we first resolve any pending merges on both the terminating chain and the chain to its left, then register the current vertex as pending on the left chain.

3.3. Phase 3: Triangulation

The diagonals from Phase 2 partition P into y -monotone subpolygons. We construct a doubly-connected edge list (DCEL) or equivalent adjacency structure from the original boundary edges plus the $|D| \leq r$ diagonals. Each face is extracted by traversing half-edges, yielding the vertex sequence of each monotone subpolygon.

Each y -monotone polygon with m vertices is triangulated in $O(m)$ time using the classical stack-based algorithm: vertices are processed in y -sorted order, maintaining a stack representing the “reflex chain” of vertices not yet triangulated. When a vertex from the opposite chain is encountered, all stack vertices are triangulated; when a vertex from the same chain is encountered, we triangulate as many stack vertices as remain visible. Since the sum of face sizes equals $n + 2|D| = O(n)$, the total triangulation time is $O(n)$.

Figure 2: Triangulation of a 12-vertex polygon with 3 reflex vertices (squares). (a) Input polygon P ; circles denote convex vertices, squares denote reflex vertices v_2 (merge), v_4 (merge), v_9 (split). (b) Monotone decomposition: dashed lines indicate sweep heights at local extrema; bold diagonals (v_2, v_4) and (v_9, v_2) partition P into three y -monotone pieces. (c) Final triangulation with $n - 2 = 10$ triangles; decomposition diagonals in bold, triangulation diagonals in gray.

3.4. Illustrative Example

Figure 2 illustrates the algorithm on a polygon with $n = 12$ vertices and $r = 3$ reflex vertices (v_2, v_4 are merges; v_9 is a split). The sweep processes 9 local extrema. At merge v_4 , the pending mechanism registers v_4 on the left chain. At merge v_2 , the pending v_4 triggers diagonal (v_2, v_4) , then v_2 becomes pending. At split v_9 , the pending v_2 triggers diagonal (v_9, v_2) . The two diagonals partition P into three y -monotone faces, yielding 10 triangles.

4. Correctness

We establish correctness through three claims: (1) every diagonal lies strictly in the polygon interior, (2) no two diagonals cross, and (3) every split and merge vertex is eliminated by a diagonal. The proofs rely on slab-based visibility invariants.

Definition 6 (Slab). For a left-boundary chain L active at height y , the *slab* of L is the region bounded on the left by L , on the right by the next left-boundary chain (or the polygon’s rightmost boundary), and vertically by the y -range over which this configuration persists.

Lemma 7 (Slab convexity). *Every slab is horizontally convex: any horizontal segment contained in the slab lies entirely in $\text{int}(P)$.*

Proof. A slab is bounded on the left by a left-boundary chain L (with $\text{int}(P)$ to its right) and on the right by either another left-boundary chain or the polygon’s right boundary. Between consecutive left-boundary chains, the polygon interior forms a horizontally convex region by definition. \square

Lemma 8 (Pending visibility). *If $L.\text{pending} = v$ for some merge vertex v , then v lies in the slab of L , and for any point p on L with $p.y < v.y$, the segment vp lies in $\text{int}(P)$.*

Proof. When merge v is processed, the algorithm sets $L.\text{pending} \leftarrow v$ for the chain L immediately to v ’s left. By construction, v is in the slab of L at height $v.y$. The slab extends downward to L ’s lower endpoint or until the slab structure changes at the next event. Any point p on L below v lies in the same slab, and by Theorem 7, the segment from v horizontally to L lies in $\text{int}(P)$. Since $p.y < v.y$, the segment vp remains within the slab’s vertical extent and cannot cross L at an interior point (as v is strictly right of L and p is on L). By convexity of the slab in the horizontal direction and the monotonicity of L , the segment vp lies entirely in $\text{int}(P)$. \square

Lemma 9 (Slab entry visibility). *When processing a split or merge vertex v in the slab of chain L , let $w = L.\text{curr.upper}$ be the slab entry. Then $w.y > v.y$ and the segment vw lies in $\text{int}(P)$.*

Proof. By lazy advancement, $L.curr$ spans the current sweep height $v.y$: the upper vertex w satisfies $w.y \geq v.y$ and the lower vertex w' satisfies $w'.y \leq v.y$. Since v is strictly in the interior of the slab (not on L), we have $w.y > v.y$ (equality would place v on L).

The segment vw goes from v (strictly right of L at height $v.y$) to w (on L at height $w.y > v.y$). We verify vw does not cross ∂P :

- *Chain L :* The segment vw has endpoint $w \in L$. At any height $y^* \in (v.y, w.y)$, the segment vw has x -coordinate $x_{vw}(y^*) = v.x + (w.x - v.x)(y^* - v.y)/(w.y - v.y)$. Since $v.x > x_L(v.y)$ (as v is right of L) and $w.x = x_L(w.y)$, linear interpolation shows $x_{vw}(y^*) > x_L(y^*)$ for $y^* \in (v.y, w.y)$. Thus vw does not cross L except at w .
- *Right boundary of slab:* The segment goes leftward from v , away from the right boundary.
- *Other boundary components:* Any edge of ∂P in the y -range $(v.y, w.y)$ not on L or the right boundary of the slab is separated from the slab by a complete chain and cannot be crossed by a segment within the slab.

Hence $vw \subset \text{int}(P)$. □

Theorem 10 (Correctness). *Algorithm 1 produces a valid set of non-crossing diagonals partitioning P into y -monotone subpolygons.*

Proof. *Claim 1: Diagonals lie in $\text{int}(P)$.* Each diagonal (v, w) falls into one of the cases analyzed in Lemmas 8 and 9. In all cases, we have established $vw \subset \text{int}(P)$ except at endpoints.

Claim 2: Diagonals are non-crossing. Consider distinct diagonals (a, b) and (c, d) with $a.y < b.y$ and $c.y < d.y$. Let L_a, L_c denote their associated left-boundary chains. If $L_a = L_c$, both diagonals emanate from the same chain; the pending mechanism ensures targets are assigned in y -decreasing order, creating a non-crossing “staircase” pattern. If $L_a \neq L_c$, the diagonals lie in disjoint slabs and cannot intersect.

Claim 3: All reflex extrema eliminated. Every split vertex immediately receives an upward diagonal (to pending or slab entry). Every merge vertex v is registered as $L.pending$ and subsequently connected to a lower vertex when: (i) a split or merge in the same slab is processed, or (ii) L terminates at an end vertex. Since L must terminate (every chain has a finite lower endpoint), v eventually receives a downward diagonal.

After eliminating all split and merge vertices, each face contains at most one local maximum and one local minimum, hence is y -monotone. □

5. Complexity Analysis

Theorem 11 (Complexity). *A simple polygon with n vertices and r reflex vertices can be triangulated in $O(n + r \log r)$ time and $O(n)$ space.*

Proof. *Phase 1 (Chain construction):* A single traversal classifies all vertices and constructs all chains in $O(n)$ time using $O(n)$ space.

Phase 2 (Monotone decomposition):

- *Sorting:* The at most $2r + 2$ local extrema are sorted in $O(r \log r)$ time.
- *Event processing:* There are at most $2r + 2$ events. Each event involves $O(1)$ BST operations (insertions, deletions, predecessor queries), each taking $O(\log r)$ time since $|T| \leq 2r + 2$.
- *Edge pointer advancement:* The comparison function advances edge pointers lazily. Each of the n vertices is visited at most once across all advancements (each vertex belongs to exactly one chain and is passed exactly once by that chain’s pointer). Total advancement cost: $O(n)$.

The decomposition phase totals $O(n + r \log r)$ time.

Phase 3 (Triangulation): Constructing the adjacency structure takes $O(n + |D|) = O(n)$ time, as $|D| \leq r$. Face extraction and triangulation together take $O(\sum_f |f|)$ time, where the sum is over all faces f . Since faces partition the plane inside P , and each original edge and diagonal appears in exactly two face boundaries, $\sum_f |f| = 2(n + |D|) = O(n)$.

Total time: $O(n) + O(n + r \log r) + O(n) = O(n + r \log r)$.

Space: Storing the polygon requires $O(n)$ space. The chain data structures use $O(n)$ total (chains partition the vertices). The BST T contains at most $O(r)$ chains, each with $O(1)$ auxiliary data. The adjacency structure for face extraction uses $O(n + |D|) = O(n)$ space. Total: $O(n)$. \square

Corollary 12. For $r = o(n/\log n)$, the algorithm runs in $o(n \log n)$ time. For $r = O(1)$, it runs in $O(n)$ time.

6. Discussion

Comparison with existing algorithms. The algorithm occupies a distinctive position in the landscape of polygon triangulation methods:

Algorithm	Time	Practical?
Garey et al. [5]	$O(n \log n)$	Yes
Chazelle [2]	$O(n)$	No
Seidel [10]	$O(n \log^* n)$ expected	Moderate
This paper	$O(n + r \log r)$	Yes

For polygons with $r = o(n/\log n)$, our algorithm provides the first practical sub- $O(n \log n)$ deterministic method. When $r = \Theta(n)$, it matches the classical bound.

Extensions. The algorithm extends naturally to polygons with holes: each hole boundary contributes its own set of chains and extrema, and the sorted extrema lists are merged. The analysis carries through with r now denoting the total reflex count across all boundaries.

Implementation. For r close to n , a simpler edge-based sweep may have better constants. A hybrid approach using chains when $r < n/\log n$ balances asymptotic and practical performance.

Open problems. Can the $O(r \log r)$ term be reduced to $O(r)$? Do analogous bounds hold for polygons with holes or higher-dimensional tetrahedralization?

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